

Power resources and grassroots activism

Worker organising potentials in logistics centres and online food delivery in Poland

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ABSTRACT

In the context of debates about logistics as a critical infrastructure of contemporary capitalism, this article addresses the question of the conditions under which workers' structural power can be translated into the organisation of collective interests. Based on original empirical research (30 interviews) in online food delivery and logistic centres in Poland, the article argues that 'organising potential' is greater in the latter. This finding is explained by the innovative activities of new, radical and grassroots trade union leaders and the availability of 'societal power resources', including the presence of Amazon as a global target of union protest (a 'reverse Amazon effect') and more developed union solidarity networks.

KEY WORDS

logistics; power resources approach; Poland; trade union organising

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Introduction

The logistics industry encompasses the management of supply chains, including design, ordering, production, transportation, warehousing, and sales (Bonacich & Wilson, 2008). Due to the structural power of workers who can disturb the smooth circulation

of capital and goods, logistics hubs have been labelled as ‘choke points’ of global capitalism (Alimahomed-Wilson & Ness, 2018). Although some logistics segments, such as rail and air transport, were well-unionised in the 20th century (Silver, 2003), the advent of lean management, privatisation and liberalisation has led to work precarisation and weakened workers’ organisations (Bonacich & Wilson, 2008; Mendonça, 2020). Notably, these challenging conditions have also spurred collective mobilisation, protests and union organising, particularly during crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic (Bessa et al., 2022; Kassem, 2023). This raises a bigger question, one which this article addresses: what are the conditions that enable workers to enact this latent structural power and organise collectively in union-hostile environments within logistics?

To answer this question, the notion of ‘organising potentials’ is proposed, to consolidate the existing literature and to understand the interaction of different types of power and their combination into resources and capabilities that workers can enact collectively. Based on narrative and focus group interviews with workers, as well as expert interviews with trade unionists and employers, the main part of this article explores organising potentials between 2020 and 2024 in the case of two segments of logistics within the private sector in Poland: logistic centres (warehouses)¹ and online food delivery. These segments were selected due to their contrasting types of work organisation and the emergence of new trade unions and workers’ protests in the period studied, allowing for a comparative analysis of factors driving collective resistance.

Poland, which is characterised by a relatively weak union presence in private logistics, has nonetheless seen innovative union practices emerge (Bernaciak & Trif, 2023). Analysis of these practices can provide insights into worker agency in resisting precarious conditions (Turner, 2009). Yet research on union organising in Eastern European logistics is still limited compared to Western Europe and North America (Alimahomed-Wilson & Ness, 2018; Goldmann, 2023; Mrozowicki & Pilch, 2021). Moreover, despite a growing body of studies of worker resistance in various logistical segments (Alimahomed-Wilson & Ness, 2018; Kassem, 2023; Vandaele et al., 2024), comparisons of mechanisms, barriers, and outcomes across these segments, such as warehousing and courier services, are scarce (Kassem, 2022). Exceptions notwithstanding (Tassinari & Maccarrone, 2020; Atzeni, 2010), relatively little research has addressed the problem of the relationship between the power potential expressed in workers’ resources and the mechanisms of their activation in different logistics segments, or what Korpi (1985) described as ‘power in use’. Addressing this problem requires a more in-depth study of union activism and leadership than in many previous studies.

In addressing these gaps, the analysis in this article documents a greater collective mobilisation in logistics centres in comparison to online food delivery workers between 2020 and 2024. This outcome is attributed to the innovative activities of radical union leaders and greater ‘societal power resources’ in warehousing, which rely on the better

1 In this article, we use the categories of logistics centres and (large) warehouses interchangeably to denote facilities that offer comprehensive services for receiving, storing and transferring goods.

visibility of Amazon as a global target of trade union protests and the expansion of internal and external union solidarity networks. As such, the article's analysis advances existing research on the role of grassroots union activism and leadership (Turner, 2009) and societal power for building collective worker organisations when other resources are deteriorating (Butković et al., 2022; Meardi, 2024). Focusing on the role of workers' power, resources and agency, the article also contributes to the analysis of essential workers' protests during the COVID-19 pandemic. (McCallum, 2022; Kassem, 2023). The article begins by outlining the concept of 'organising potentials', synthesising insights from various power resources theories and literature on worker mobilisation in logistics. It proceeds with a methodological section, followed by case studies from the two industry segments, and concludes with a discussion of the findings.

Organising potentials in logistics: a literature review

The analysis of workers' power resources was a response to debates on the growing power of employers in the context of neoliberal globalisation (Arnholtz & Refslund, 2024). As Meardi (2024) notes, the two main streams of discussion on power resources include Korpi's (1985) classic power resources theory and neo-Marxist theories drawing on and developing Wright's (2000) and later on Silver's (2003) conceptualisations. In both cases, the analysis aims to understand how various kinds of resources can be mobilised by workers to counteract the structural asymmetry between capital and labour (Arnholtz & Refslund, 2024). Korpi (1985:31) defines power resources as 'attributes (capacities or means) of actors (individuals or collectives), which enable them to reward or punish other actors'. Looking at resources makes it possible to explore the potentials of power *before* it is used (Meardi, 2024), i.e. before power resources are 'activated' (Korpi, 1985) in relation to other actors. While neo-Marxist approaches have focused on enacted power, Korpi's original analysis explored the distribution of power resources between the major social classes as potentials in relation to the achievement of economic democracy and class compromise (cf. Meardi, 2024).

Most (but not all) of the contemporary approaches to workers' power resources depart from the basic distinctions made by Wright (2000) between structural power and associational power. The former is understood as 'the location of workers within an economic system' (Wright, 2000:962). This was further divided by Silver (2003:13) into marketplace bargaining power (involving scarce skills among other factors) and workplace bargaining power.² The associational power results from the development of workers' collective organisation, in particular that arising from trade unions (Wright, 2000:962). More recently, Schmalz et al. (2018) have distinguished between institutional and societal power resources. The former concern 'institutionalised labour rights and institutionalised dialogue procedures' (Schmalz et al., 2018:115),

2 Workplace bargaining power is understood as the 'strategic location of a particular group of workers within a key industrial sector' (Wright, 2000:962).

including collective bargaining and strike regulations. In turn, societal power resources are based on two types of power: coalitional power, based on the links of workers' organisations with other social and political actors, and discursive power, understood as the capacity of workers' organisations to intervene in public debates, define problems and propose solutions (Schmalz et al., 2018:122–23). Discursive power overlaps with, even if it is not identical to, symbolic power, defined by Jeniffer Chun (2009) as workers' capacity for winning public recognition and legitimacy for their struggles, among others, by attracting media attention and framing workers' demands in moral terms.

Focusing on the sources of union (rather than worker) power, and drawing on social movement theories, Levesque and Murray (2010:336) proposed their own conceptualisation of power resources, albeit one that overlaps with existing ones (Table 1). Internal solidarity ('collective cohesion and deliberative vitality') and infrastructural resources ('the material and human resources') are important sources of associational power. External solidarity ('horizontal and vertical links with other unions and with community groups and social movements'), resembling 'coalitional power', and narrative resources ('the existing stock of stories that frame understandings and union actions'), akin to the notion of discursive power, are the sources of societal power.

Meardi (2024) notes that distinct power resources can be conceptualised as either substituting for or complementing one another. A specific configuration, or interaction, of power resources enables the pursuit of certain actions while constraining others (Brookes, 2013). According to Arnholtz and Refslund (2024:16–18), it is the formation of preferences (perceived interests) and strategies aimed at pursuing preferences that lead to the creation of collectives that can make use of available resources. In other words, it is up to trade union activists and leaders to identify resources, make strategic choices between them and use them for the purposes of collective mobilisation. This is

Table 1: Conceptual mapping of workers' power resources

The main types of workers' power resources	The sources of workers' power
Structural power resources	Marketplace power Workplace power
Associational power resources	Internal solidarity Infrastructural and human resources
Institutional power resources	Institutionalised labour rights and social dialogue procedures
Societal power resources	Coalitional power (or external solidarity) Discursive and symbolic power (or narrative resources)

Source: Authors' elaboration based on Refslund & Arnholtz, 2024; Schmalz et al., 2018; Chun, 2009; Levesque & Murray, 2010

where Levesque and Murray's (2010) approach can complement Korpi and Wright's theories as it focuses on the role of capabilities in activating power resources; capabilities are defined, in this context, as the 'sets of aptitudes, competencies, abilities, social skills or know-how that can be developed, transmitted and learned' (Levesque & Murray, 2010:335).

Some existing research shows that the socio-economic and institutional context is likely to lead to certain strategic choices. For example, where institutional union resources are stronger, as they were historically in Germany, investment in union organising is less likely than in liberal market economies, where union recognition often depends on membership (Frege & Kelly 2003). However, other studies demonstrate that the social context does not influence workers' power in a deterministic way and that union leaders and activists can also use scarce resources of power in unconventional and unexpected ways (Bernaciak & Trif, 2023; Meardi, 2024; Turner, 2009). The focus on the 'strategic choices' of unions underplays the situations in which power resources are mobilised and capacities are built in the form of 'embryonic solidarities' (Atzeni, 2010), such as those observed in the protests of non-unionised food delivery couriers (Cini et al., 2021; Tassinari & Maccarone, 2020). As shown by Tassinari and Maccarone (2020), the extent to which such solidarity, which reflects workers' interdependence in the labour process and which manifests in everyday mutual support and shared grievances, can lead to the building of collective identity and, subsequently, to collective action depends on a number of contextual conditions. In this article, we propose to think of these conditions as 'organising potentials'. The article defines organising potentials as the combination of workers' diverse power resources and capabilities, and their collective agency as manifested in activism and grassroots leadership, the presence of which supports the creation of organisations that represent workers' collective interests.

Existing research suggests that logistics workers' structural power is more limited than the portrayal implied in the literature on capitalism's 'chokepoints' (Alimahomed-Wilson & Ness, 2018) and that workers' power must be analysed within its social and political context. For example, Nowak's (2022) study of the failed truck drivers' protests in Brazil highlights how the combination of its occurrence in a semi-peripheral economy and a lack of political vision negatively affected the outcomes of collective mobilisation. Marketisation and lean management have weakened union strongholds and fostered individualistic ideologies among precarious logistics workers (Bonacich & Wilson, 2008; Polkowska & Filipek, 2019). Additionally, transnational companies like Amazon and Ryanair use management techniques, surveillance, and cost-cutting strategies aimed at union-busting (Mendonça, 2010; Kassem, 2022; Vallas et al., 2022). Furthermore, platform-mediated work challenges traditional definitions of worker-employer relationships (Aloisi & De Stefano, 2020) by promoting self-employment and subcontracting. This shift, called the 'platform effect' by Hassel and Sieker (2022), is visible in the business models of Amazon and other platform companies. These 'extreme forms' (Hassel & Sieker, 2022:377) of subcontracting undermine workers' institutional power and exacerbate the erosion of collective labour relations by introducing the independent contractor model as a new norm in employment relations

across entire supply chains, shifting platform companies' responsibilities for their workers to subcontractors.

The erosion of structural and associational power has not stopped logistics workers from organising, but it has shifted the focus toward building 'societal power resources.' Studies of platform-based food delivery (Bessa et al., 2022; Cini et al., 2021; Tassinari & Maccarone, 2022) and Amazon warehouses (Kassem, 2023) show an increasing role for new, usually independent and grassroots unions and non-union organisations, which often supplement traditional trade unions.³ Synergies between old and new labour actors have been found to be crucial for sustaining unions in platform work (Marà et al., 2023). For example, the combination of workplace and societal power resources made it possible to unionise the first warehouse (JFK8 in Staten Island) by a new, independent Amazon Labor Union (ALU), during the COVID-19 pandemic (Kassem, 2023). The success of the ALU and the media attention it attracted, combined with its subsequent affiliation with a traditional union, the Teamsters, which conducted a strategic organising campaign at several other Amazon sites in the USA, was arguably an important factor in helping to organise a national strike in late 2024 (Mena, 2024). Unions leveraged the 'essential work' narrative to mobilise and legitimise worker demands both locally and internationally (McCallum, 2022). Regarding external solidarities, transnational coalitions of unions are important in logistics because they help workers to challenge employers by combining structural, institutional and societal power resources that can be deployed to disrupt distribution, influence regulations and damage corporate reputations (Brokes, 2013; Goldmann, 2023; Mendonça, 2010).

Despite a growing body of research on worker mobilisation in logistics, some gaps and areas for further research can be identified. Most existing studies focus on single companies such as Amazon (Kassem, 2022; 2023; Vallas et al., 2022) or specific branches of industry; for instance, platform work (Cini et al., 2021; Marà et al., 2023), airlines (Mendonça, 2020), ports (Bonacich & Wilson, 2008) or truck transport (Nowak, 2022). One of the exceptions is the work of Kassem (2022) in Germany, who compared the workplace power of Amazon warehouse workers and Mechanical Turk (MT) workers. She concluded that location-based work helped warehouse workers increase their power during the COVID-19 pandemic compared to Amazon MT workers, whose power as web-based workers decreased. Our article builds on this conclusion by comparing two location-based logistics segments of which one represents a more traditional, quasi-Fordist work organisation (logistics centres) and the second Internet-based gig work (online food delivery) in Poland.

Reflecting observations about the non-deterministic role played by the socio-economic and institutional context, the concept of 'organising potential' bridges the analysis of the main types of workers' power resources with the literature on workers' activism to understand the role of the latter in activating the former. While the existing

3 We follow the distinction between traditional unions and new unions proposed by Bessa et al. (2022:11). New unions are usually 'recently founded, small, politically radical, non-affiliated to national confederations, and with a militant and bottom-up approach to organising'. Traditional unions, in turn, tend to be 'longstanding, large, politically more moderate (social democratic), affiliated to national federations, and with a more moderate approach to organising that is more likely to be directed by union officers'.

research focuses on structural and institutional factors at the macro- and organisational levels, we are particularly interested in the conditions of 'organising potentials' at the micro-level of workplace crews and collectives, and, more precisely, in the role of labour activists in mobilising workers under structurally difficult circumstances.

The case of Poland: methods and data

Although research has highlighted the potential for union innovation in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) (Bernaciak & Trif, 2023), few studies have examined the collective organisation of logistics workers in the region. CEE has traditionally been seen as a site for relocating logistics to increase profitability and weaken Western European trade unions rather than a site where workers' power can be fostered locally (Kassem, 2022; Zanoni & Miszczyński, 2024). Recent studies have highlighted issues such as Amazon's workforce fragmentation (Zanoni & Miszczyński, 2024), the invisibility of unions to gig workers (Polkowska, 2021), and ways in which food couriers prioritise 'loyalty' over collective voice (Muszyński et al., 2022). Research has also indicated an erosion of collective labour relations in road transport and postal services in the course of their marketisation since the late 1990s (Kozek, 2011). However, studies in Poland have identified the potential for union development in logistics companies such as Amazon and platform economy companies through smaller, politically radical unions such as the left-wing Workers' Initiative (Maciejewska & Mrozowicki, 2017). The emergence of both radical and traditional trade unions at Amazon has played a prefigurative role in organising private logistics companies since the mid-2010s, with worker protests intensifying during the COVID-19 pandemic (Mrozowicki & Pilch, 2021).

This article focuses on the two logistics segments where workers' collective mobilisation was most visible from 2020 to 2024, logistics centres and online food delivery services, in order to understand the nexus of contextual factors, power resources and worker activism that made resistance possible. The choice of Poland as a case study allows us to explore workers' 'organising potentials' in a country which is located at the crossroads of West-East trade routes and characterised by a growing internal market with relatively low labour costs (Mrozowicki & Pilch, 2021; Zanoni & Miszczyński, 2024). In contrast to many other EU countries, where employment in logistics has declined or stagnated over the last decade, transport and warehousing in Poland employed more than 946,000 people in 2020, 30 per cent more than in 2009 (Eurostat SBS, n.d.). Although precise statistics are missing, the number of migrant workers in the industry has been steadily increasing in recent years. In 2021, almost 21 per cent of the total work permits for foreigners were issued in transport and warehousing, the majority of which were granted to Ukrainians and Belarusians (GUS, 2022).

To explore the organising potential of a diversified workforce in Polish logistics, various data collection techniques were employed. Biographical Narrative Interviews (BNIs) (Schütze, 2016) and Focus Group Interviews (FGIs) with workers facilitated an understanding of individual and collective agency. BNIs enabled retrospective

examination of workers' experiences and life strategies, spanning both professional and personal spheres. FGIs helped reconstruct how opinions on job quality dimensions such as job security, working hours, income, autonomy, and collective representation are shaped. Expert interviews (Döringer, 2021) with trade union and employer representatives made it possible to understand the role of institutional factors, structural challenges and the impact of crises like COVID-19 on worker organising and social dialogue. Additional information (e.g. union positions) was also gathered from trade union websites and social media profiles.

Between 2021 and 2023, 18 biographical interviews were conducted with workers in two Polish logistics sectors: online food delivery (9) and logistics centres/warehouses (9). Participants were recruited via social networks and online advertisements, aiming for diversity in age, gender, company, union membership and ethnicity. Most were cisgender men ($M = 12$, $F = 5$, $N/A = 1$), aged 35 on average, residing in cities with over 100,000 inhabitants ($N = 13$); five were migrant workers from Ukraine and Belarus. From February to April 2022, three additional FGIs with 18 participants (including 13 men, two Ukrainian citizens and two union members) were carried out in the Warsaw region in logistics centres (2) and online food delivery (1). The FGIs were conducted online by a research company with the participation of the authors, who also provided the scripts for the interviews. Additionally, eight expert interviews were held with union and employer representatives.

All interviews collected were recorded and then transcribed and anonymised⁴. Notes were taken during the interviews and analytical summaries were then produced. In the first stage, the empirical data were thematically coded using Atlas.ti software (Gibbs, 2007). The structure of the codes reflected the core themes in the data, which were reconstructed both inductively, through line-by-line labelling of the content of the transcripts, and deductively, with reference to our 'theoretical sensitivity' (Glaser, 1978). The latter was based on our knowledge of the industry under study and existing conceptual frameworks. In the second stage, a concept of 'organising potential' was developed through 'theoretical coding' (Glaser, 1978) to link the emerging thematic codes with different types and sources of workers' power and the manifestations of their individual and collective agency.

Food delivery couriers

Before 2020, there were only failed attempts to organise trade unions in online food delivery, including Uber Eats (EX_23_L). From 2020 onwards, two new unions emerged: the Confederation of Labour, a left-wing union affiliated to OPZZ⁵ was

4 In the rest of the article, we use the following pattern to quote our interviewees: Pseudonym_Interview number_Interview type_(EX=expert, BNI – biographical narrative interview, FGI – focus group interview) L (Logistics). For expert interviews we do not use pseudonyms, so they are only identified by numbers.

5 The All-Poland Alliance of Trade Unions, a traditional union, one of the largest union confederations in Poland.

created in Pyszne.pl⁶ in autumn 2022, and a smaller, politically radical, anarcho-syndicalist Workers' Initiative of Couriers emerged in spring 2024 in the wake of grassroots workers' protests at Glovo. Earlier, in the spring of 2021, non-unionised Glovo workers demanded a pay rise and went on a wildcat strike, organising themselves via social media, including a Facebook event and groups, and sabotaging the application's functionality. Marcin, one of the leaders of this spontaneous protest, describes how the couriers were mobilised. His narrative points to the combination of 'embryonic solidarity' (Atzeni, 2010), or nascent associational power, with discursive power based on social media groups:

I communicated very well with a lot of people, we formed another group, the kind of Glovo team that talks the most ... And for a whole week, we kept motivating ourselves so that we would go on strike ... So I said, I'll try it. I created a Facebook event called 'Strike Glovo' and announced that we were on strike.
(BNI_1_L_Marcin)

Our analysis suggests that both contextual and agential factors contributed to the rise of workers' protests, with the former being explicitly mentioned by some participants. For example, Glovo couriers cited the reduction of bonuses and the worsening of wage regulations after the peak of the pandemic as the reason for the protests (BNI_1_L_Marcin) and workers at Pyszne.pl referred to the lack of wage increases, which did not compensate for the increase in the prices of basic goods: 'What annoys and mobilises people most is the fact that their delivery conditions are deteriorating' (BNI_20_L_Damian). Many participants also mentioned that during the period of COVID-19, their work was recognised as socially important by clients ('we are seen now as more needed' [FGI_13_L], 'some [clients] were really grateful' [BNI_04_L_Zuza]). The perceived social importance of their work could be seen as a potential for building societal power. However, this potential was not mentioned by the union leaders interviewed, reflecting a general lack of reference to the 'essential work' discourse in Poland (Gardawski et al., 2022).⁷

Another contextual factor that facilitated collective mobilisation in the food delivery segment is related to the emerging institutional resources linked to the consultations on the EU Directive on improving working conditions in platform work. These resources were explicitly mentioned by trade union leaders as an opportunity to influence the process of implementation by developing links with political parties and international trade unions, thus building societal power resources (EX_23_L).⁸ On the one hand, the interviews document the potential of coalitional power which involved building a network of international contacts among unionists operating in different EU

6 Pyszne.pl is a Polish branch of Just Eat Takeaway.

7 While the media in Poland referred to the category of 'heroes' when writing about workers in key public services in the pandemic, the concept of essential labour was not present in the crisis legislation and only occasionally appeared in the media. Unlike in other countries (Stevano et al., 2021), the concept also had no historical precedents (e.g. in relation to war or natural disasters).

8 For example, a joint position paper from OPZZ, Solidarity and the ETUC was sent to the Minister for Family and Social Policy in November 2002 to highlight the social partners' views on the draft Directive.

countries under the Just Eat Takeaway brand (BNI_20_L_Damian). On the other hand, debate on the Directive brought the problems of couriers to the attention of the media. All union activists interviewed, as well as posts on the Facebook profile of the Workers' Initiative of Couriers⁹, referred to a very high level of media interest in workers' protests, indicating a potential for the development of discursive power. Some platforms, most notably Pyszne.pl, also saw benefits in working with trade unions in the context of the expected regulatory changes in the platform economy in the EU:

The trade union was established simply because it could be established. And this is the exception, as it were, in comparison with our competitors ... but this is part ... of a trend to regulate the industry. (EX_35_L)

However, contextual factors alone cannot explain collective mobilisation. Our data show that trade union support for grassroots mobilisation and the emergence of new union leaders were key factors facilitating successful union organising in Pyszne.pl. While no union took advantage of the spontaneous protests in Glovo in 2021, the Confederation of Labour OPZZ was able to identify and capitalise on the dissatisfaction with the wages and working conditions of Pyszne.pl workers. It organised a picnic in front of the OPZZ headquarters in Warsaw in September 2022 ('it was about having a place where we could talk to these people', EX_23_L), gathering couriers by mass ordering food from Pyszne.pl to attract media attention, to build links with workers and organise future union members. This was followed by several protest actions, including informal work stoppages in December 2022 and the publication of a 'Platform Workers' Manifesto' in the media.

The crucial aspect of organising was the employment of one of the OPZZ youth members as a courier ('He is employed there, and being inside it also gave this [union organising – AM] such, such credibility', EX_23_L). Damian, a grassroots leader and co-founder of the Confederation of Labour union at Pyszne.pl, is also an active member of left-wing, literary and academic circles, and a former tenant movement activist. His story demonstrates that earlier activist experiences and networks might be important factors in the success of a workers' organisation:

Through a friend in literary circles, I met a colleague from the Youth of the Confederation of Labour. And it turned out that he was actually the initiator [of the collective mobilisation] in Pyszne.pl. And they had secured some funding for it from the trade union. So they said I could take part. And we actually did such an action.¹⁰ (BNI_20_L_Damian)

The story of organising in Pyszne.pl shows that the key to activating organising potentials in this industry is the activity of innovative trade union leaders capable of bridging bottom-up actions with established union structures, securing material resources and political support for new organisations (cf. Marà et al., 2023). It takes the

9 Inicjatywa Pracownicza Kurierów: <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61557813846724> [Accessed 11 January 2025]

10 A picnic for couriers.

political imagination of leaders at the national level to see the long-term benefits of organising platform workers, as in the case of the Confederation of Labour leadership:

In the short term there will certainly not be any financial results, or any results that translate into the material part of the union. In the long term, however, this is an extremely important subject for us, because we have a very large group of people, growing all the time, who work on virtually unknown principles.¹¹
(EX_23_L)

Despite tangible progress in organising at Pyszne.pl and recent developments at Glovo, with several dozen union members in both companies, unionisation in online food delivery in Poland is still at a very early stage. Although the need for food delivery services initially grew during the first waves of the pandemic (Polkowska, 2020), the structural power resources of app-based couriers did not increase due to fluctuating demand and their particular employment status in which precarious civil law contracts offered by labour intermediaries are dominant ('the company washes its hands' [Wojtek_BNI_17_L]) (Muszyński et al., 2022). Couriers' working conditions are marked by extreme employment flexibility and non-transparency, underpinned by algorithms, as documented in a conversation of FGI participants:

Sonia: *I wasn't getting that last order for which I could already get that bonus ...*
Moderator: *Was it bad luck, coincidence or why was that happening?*
Sonia: *I think it was on purpose.*
Lech: *The algorithm.*

Despite the precarity of their employment, workers rarely turn to trade unions because of their very limited knowledge of union activities and the very small union presence in the sector. Opinions among non-unionised workers indicate the limited effects of unions' discursive power for changing the image of worker organisations:

I don't know [unions] at all, I mean, on what principle it works. I know that in communism I think there were unions in general. (BNI_03_L_Grzegorz)
Maybe there are [trade unions] in the [employer's] office, but it doesn't affect us, and I don't know too much about them [laughs]. (BNI_02_L_Maria)

The composition of the workforce, which is dominated by young people, students and migrants, was also cited by some trade union leaders (EX_23_L) and experts (EX_25) as an obstacle to organising. They pointed to language problems and high turnover, echoing arguments familiar in the literature about the reluctance of unions to invest scarce resources in organising such 'difficult' groups (Alberti & Sacchetto, 2024). It should be noted, however, that migrant and younger workers are among the leaders of the newly formed Workers Initiative of Couriers, which suggests that such barriers are not insurmountable¹². The case of organising at Pyszne.pl shows that successful

11 By 'unknown principles', the union leader means very precarious working and employment conditions ('junk contracts', i.e. various service contracts not regulated by the Labour Code).

12 A migrant activist from the Workers' Initiative of Couriers was one of the panelists at the conference 'Social Boundaries of Work' in Wrocław, co-organised by the authors of the article, on 16 October 2024.

organising in the sector is a process in which a convergence of contextual factors related to broader political (regulatory) contexts and committed union leaders at the national and platform ('company') level is necessary.

Logistics centres in Poland and the case of Amazon Poland

Compared to online food delivery, which was estimated by participants to employ around 8,000 people at the time of our interviews (EX_35_L), there were over 215,000 warehouse workers in Poland in 2022, according to Statistics Poland data. Amazon directly and indirectly (i.e., via agencies) employs between 15 and 20 per cent of these (EX_03_L), making the company's labour situation an important reference point for the entire industry and the main subject of our analysis in this section.

Although work stoppages in logistics centres can be potentially damaging to employers because of their employment in 'critical nodes in the global capitalist supply chain' (Alimahomed-Wilson & Ness, 2018:2), the structural and associational power of workers is weakened by several factors that emerged from interviews with Amazon workers and trade unionists. First, the workforce is fragmented and precarious, largely due to agency work. Work and pay rules are subject to algorithmic control rather than union consultation ('we as a trade union have no influence in setting the quotas', EX_5_L). Second, legal strikes are limited by the Polish labour law, which requires 50 per cent of all workers to participate in a strike vote, making it almost impossible to organise in large employers like Amazon ('we can't actually go on strike because the law ... simply makes it impossible' [EX_5_L]).¹³ Third, Amazon employs a range of anti-union practices ranging from 'outright dismissals, intimidation, non-stop letters of discipline' (EX_25_L) and preventing unions from holding an effective strike referendum, to organising employer-controlled 'Associates' Forums' to substitute for unions (EX_20_L).

A fourth challenge for trade unions is an increasingly diverse workforce, including a large share of younger workers and immigrants whose presence is seen by some unionists as a means of undermining unionisation ('if you don't want to work, we'll take five thousand Ukrainians, they'll do it for half the wage' [BNI_15_L_Stefan]). Although there is an organising potential among migrant workers (as stated by one non-unionised participant, 'I would have joined [a union] if I knew how' [BNI_22_L_Aksana]), the opinions of non-unionised workers are similar to those of food delivery workers, expressing scepticism about union activities and a focus on individualistic strategies at work:

The unions do more harm than good ... They're a bit weak ... I consider myself a resourceful worker ... In a place like Amazon, if you're reasonably savvy, you need to work smart, not hard. (BNI_06_L_Franek)

I'd not belong to unions, if they're in my company, I'd rather decide about myself, my problems, and solve them with the employer myself. (FGI_14_L_Bartek)

¹³ The same argument applies to food delivery, but it was not even mentioned by the participants because legal strikes are not seen as realistic for small unions.

At the same time, however, logistics centres bring together a significant number of workers into one physical location (Kassem, 2022) which – from an organising perspective – provides a greater opportunity to build associational power than in the case of mobile food delivery workers where places of work are more diffuse and less centralised. Until 2014, trade unions have existed in the ‘public’ part of the sector, i.e. marketised companies fully or partially owned by the state, including the Polish Airlines LOT, Polish Railways, and Polish Post. The situation changed in 2014 when unions were formed at Amazon’s Polish branch and a limited number of other logistic centres (e.g. NSZZ Solidarność [‘Solidarity’] in DHL, formed in 2016).

Amazon’s entry into Poland and its continued activity as a very large employer made organising its workers a strategic objective for unions. As of 2024, around 5–6 per cent of the workforce in Amazon Poland was organised into two trade unions: the grassroots radical trade union Workers’ Initiative and a smaller branch of NSZZ Solidarność (Solidarity) (EX_5_L).¹⁴ As one of the leaders of the Workers’ Initiative, who was linked to left-wing social movements and co-organised unions at Amazon in 2014, put it:

We started dealing with Amazon because we recognised the crucial importance of logistics and this global circulation of goods. (EX_3_L)

Workers’ Initiative has chosen a radical, participatory and confrontational path that has its roots in the anarchist movement (Maciejewska & Mrozowski, 2017). It relies on building union associational power based on close solidarity ties in the workplace (‘we don’t have full-time trade union officials and we want everyone to be in contact with the crew on the floor’ [EX_3_L]), as well as informal, cyclical protests in cooperation with different social movements, from which the first group of organisers also emerged. In contrast, Solidarity initially adopted a more cooperative strategy towards the employer. Its emergence was supported by professional organisers employed by the union, based, among others, on organising projects initiated by the UNI Global Union (the global union for the service industries):

We ran projects like this, with people assigned to them¹⁵. These were people who were Solidarity workers, but they would help us, as it were, to unionise more warehouses. (EX_5_L)

As with online food delivery, the context of the COVID-19 pandemic created new opportunities for further union development in relation to the increasing demand for online orders and the discourse of essential work (McCallum, 2022). In early 2020, unions at Amazon pushed for increased compensation, using an ‘Amazon heroes’ slogan invented by the workers and then hijacked by the employer (EX_3_L; EX_5_L). In 2020–2024, the Workers’ Initiative, often supported by Solidarity, combined a range of innovative protest tactics to push for wage increases, better health and safety

14 There is also a much smaller trade union at the company, namely AGROunia Pracownicza, but the number of its members is difficult to estimate. Polish labour law favours union pluralism in the workplace. The same category of workers (or job titles) can be organised by multiple unions.

15 He is contextually referring to the project funded by UNI Global Union.

regulations and protest against algorithmically-managed work intensification. These included joining international actions on Black Friday and organising strike ballots, spontaneous rallies, and blockades of logistics centres. One of the rank-and-file unionists recalled these actions and pointed to the support of activists from outside the company:

A year ago [in 2020], we had a kind of strike in front of the warehouse. We were doing a blockade. We, as trade unionists, were with the workers and supporters of the Workers' Initiative. (BNI_09_L_Igor)

Since 2020, Workers' Initiative has strategically expanded to various logistics centres ('this is our dream – to organise an entire segment' [EX_3_L]), successfully leading collective disputes in companies like Avon and L'Oreal, resulting in wage increases (Joanna_BNI_18_L)

Unions emerged also in other warehouses, including, for instance, UPS and DHL Distribution (EX_24_L). The fact that unions entered other private companies in the warehousing sector could be linked to the social network effects associated with the way that the development of associational power resources by innovative union leaders created new connections both within and outside union organisations. While some of the new activists of the Workers' Initiative at company level had a background in social movements, others, such as Joanna (or Igor, quoted previously in his article), joined the union to fight for better working conditions without any previous political experience: 'I am active by nature. I like activity in general, helping. Well, I'm such a pro-social person' (BNI_18_L_Joanna). The social network effect can be linked to the combination of 'embryonic solidarity' on the shop floor with connections to other social movements, as seen in the quote from Stefan, an activist in Amazon:

One day, my colleague mobilised the guys to do a stoppage with honking the trolleys. We did a seven-minute one [protest] with our trolleys ... And after, sometime, later we did a blockade of the warehouse in Wrocław. A lot of young people came to support us. (BNI_15_L_Stefan)

Building associational power relates to developing both internal and external solidarities, thus reflecting the development of societal power resources. The expansion of internal solidarity is demonstrated by the fact that the Workers' Initiative was the only case of a union attempting to combine protests in different segments of the logistics chain. It has supported the protests of truck drivers delivering goods to Amazon and is continuing to try to organise temporary agency workers, many of whom are migrants, even if the membership gains ('a dozen [migrant] members' [EX_24_L], i.e. 1–2 per cent of total union membership) remain limited. As far as external solidarity is concerned, both unions at Amazon relied on the established international union cooperation in Amazon Workers International and the UNI Amazon Global Alliance network (Goldman, 2023).¹⁶ It was through international contacts that certain

¹⁶ Amazon Workers International is a transnational 'bottom-up' coalition formed in 2015 by new and traditional trade union and Amazon workers' activists to coordinate protest actions across countries. The UNI Amazon Global Alliance was created in 2014 by union officials (in a more 'top-down' way) as a coalition of

actions, such as the ‘Make Amazon Pay’ initiative, were communicated to the public. International solidarity is seen as a necessary response to the shifting of supply chain operations between countries to counter workers’ strikes (EX_03_L).

Since both unions at Amazon consider their presence to be strategic because of the importance of this company in Poland and globally, their efforts can be understood as an attempt to counteract the negative Amazon effects on collective labour relations. The ‘reverse Amazon effect’, to paraphrase Hassel and Sieker’s (2022) term, is based on the political and strategic transformation of embryonic solidarity and grassroots activism into collective organisation (‘associational power’). It relies on building on societal, and in particular symbolic (Chun, 2009) power resources gained from the successful union organising of Amazon which symbolises the anti-union strategies of global capital. So far, the results of such union tactics are more visible in the case of the Workers’ Initiative than in the case of Solidarity. Not only has it managed to grow by a further 200 members (i.e. by some 25 per cent) at Amazon from 2020 to 2022, despite very high worker turnover at the company (EX_24_L); it has also expanded to other logistics companies. However, Solidarity’s press releases suggest that the union has also begun to adopt a similar model (e.g., not having full-time union officers and combining union duties with warehouse work to keep in closer contact with workers). A visible increase in membership at Amazon from 2022 to 2023 has been observed (Solidarność, 2023).

Discussion and conclusions

This article has presented original research on emerging worker protests and union organising in warehousing and online food delivery in Poland, a country where very little research has been done on union development in logistics. While a broadly conceived logistics industry has been described as a ‘chokepoint’ of global capitalism (Alimahomed-Wilson & Ness, 2018), our analysis joins existing research (Kassem, 2022, 2023) and related critiques of the power resources approach (Nowak, 2022) in showing that the structural power of workers is not sufficient to organise workers and disrupt the circulation of goods and services. The article has proposed that the concept of ‘organising potentials’ is useful to consolidate observations from the literature on power resources theory and worker activism (Arnholtz & Refslund, 2024; Meardi, 2024; Turner, 2009). Our empirical research on two, union-hostile logistics segments suggests that tangible results in terms of transforming such potential into new collective workers’ organisations require the interaction of different types of power resources, in particular societal power, with the innovative activity of trade union leaders at both company and industry level.

Contextual factors, such as the growing demand for logistics services during the COVID-19 pandemic and EU regulatory changes in the platform economy, created a new opportunity structure for union development. Our analysis suggests that Polish trade unions have made better use of this potential in the case of warehousing than in the case

traditional unions affiliated to UNI Global Union and other global union federations, advocacy groups and experts to facilitate information sharing and the organisation of global campaigns. (Goldman, 2023).

of online food delivery. This leads us to the first contribution of this study to the debates on the mechanisms of union organising in logistics, which relates to what we have proposed to call the 'reverse Amazon effect', alluding to the concept of the 'platform effect' coined by Hassel and Sieker (2022). The concept of the 'platform effect' refers to the indirect impact of platform companies, such as Amazon, on employment relationships in non-platform firms or entire sectors, leading to the spread of self-employment and subcontracting (Hassel & Sieker, 2022:364). The 'reverse Amazon effect' in turn relies on the ability of union leaders to develop and activate societal and symbolic power resources (Chun, 2009), linked to the political and moral definition of Amazon as a symbol of global labour exploitation, subcontracting and agency work, to create and support new workers' organisations in Amazon itself, its subcontractors and other logistics companies. The creation of unions in Amazon not only countered the image of Poland as a country of cheap and docile labour to which logistic operations can be relocated from better unionised Western countries (Kassem, 2022); it was also an opportunity for union leaders to experiment with developing internal solidarity against the forces of workforce fragmentation, organising agency workers, migrants and subcontracted truck drivers, and fostering external solidarity against the employer's relocation strategies by collaborating with UNI Global and Amazon Workers International. Building discursive power based on promoting tangible union gains against Amazon as a global 'Goliath' and fostering solidarity against the 'platform effect', translated into associational power not only in Amazon, but also in other logistics centres.

In the online food delivery sector, no global company comparable to Amazon has been the target of union organising campaigns. The Polish branch of Just Eat Takeaway, Pyszne.pl is an outlier rather than a model for the industry, despite its high market share. Unlike its competitors, Pyszne.pl employs workers directly and sees the benefits of a union presence. In comparison to warehousing, online food delivery is also a much smaller segment of the logistics sector, with far fewer workers employed in general, and in standard employment relations with permanent contracts in particular. This makes it less attractive for unions in terms of the potential for membership growth. As in other countries (Cini et al., 2021; Marà et al., 2023; Tassinari & Maccarone, 2020), the existence of 'embryonic solidarities' rooted in day-to-day work experience and shared grievances led to an outburst of spontaneous protests in various platform companies, including Pyszne.pl, Glovo and Uber Eats. But it was only in the cases of Pyszne.pl and, ultimately, Glovo that protests turned into unionisation, with the unions supporting spontaneous workers' mobilisations. On this point, our research confirms the observations of Marà et al. (2023) that there is a need to link grassroots activists with the institutional resources of established trade union organisations to make tangible gains in the platform economy.

The second important contribution of our analysis concerns the role of new, often smaller, grassroots and radical political trade unions in gaining ground in the difficult organising terrains of food delivery and warehousing. Protest-based organising and the emphasis on breaking down barriers between trade unionists and workers, which was initially promoted by the anarcho-syndicalist Workers Initiative, has also been adopted by a traditional trade union, Solidarity, at Amazon, and by the Confederation of Labour in Pyszne.pl. Our research contributes to understanding how new radical unions can

drive change within the trade union movement, especially in food delivery (Cini et al., 2021; Marà et al., 2023) and warehousing (Amazon Workers and Supporters, 2018; Kassem, 2023; Mrozowicki & Maciejewska, 2017). In the USA, the Amazon Labor Union (ALU) has failed to expand beyond a single fulfilment centre on Staten Island in New York (known as JFK8 – see Kassem, 2023) and, ultimately, in 2024, joined forces with the nationwide Teamsters union. It was different in Poland, where the Workers' Initiative has begun on its own to make inroads into Amazon subcontractors and other companies in the industry. But in both cases, it was small, autonomous unions that led the initial organising drive against the US giant.

However, there are limits to radical unions' tactics related to their limited associational and institutional power resources, which is most visible in restrictive strike laws that make it almost impossible to strike legally in companies such as Amazon in Poland. While this is a reason for further experimentation, regulatory changes will be required to enable the building of institutional power and, possibly, better cooperation between new and traditional unions. The study of cooperation between radical and traditional trade unions in logistics is an important field for further research and one of the limitations of the analyses presented in the article.

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